

DISPERSION IN SLOW WAVE TWO-LAYERED SEMICONDUCTOR
LOADED PARALLEL-PLATE WAVEGUIDE

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Introduction: Original interest in two-layer loaded microstrip lines occurred because of integrated circuit applications where a thin dielectric layer was fabricated over a semiconductor substrate which was several hundred times its thickness. Due to the slow wave behavior of such a structure, theoretical and experimental investigations have been completed with interest lying in a broad range of applications for the structure and its variable phase velocity version utilizing an applied dc bias to the metal line [1]-[5]. The dc bias is used to create a space charge depletion layer under the dielectric and hence modulate the dielectric's effective thickness. A variant of the dielectric-semiconductor loaded structure uses a Schottky barrier line over the semiconductor. The depletion layer will then serve as the replacement for the dielectric. Possible applications include distributed amplifiers, variable phase shifters, voltage-tunable filters, distributed FETs, delay lines, and variable coupling coefficient directional couplers. Work to date has focused primarily on microwave frequencies, mostly below 10 GHz. Furthermore, the theoretical work has treated only the first branch TM_0 of the dispersion curve (fundamental mode¹). In order to assess the potential uses of the slow wave structure at millimeter wave frequencies, knowledge of the higher mode branches is obtained in this paper for $10 \text{ GHz} \leq f \leq 140 \text{ GHz}$.

Theory: For wide microstrip lines, a parallel-plate waveguide model (Fig. 1) should yield reasonable results. Medium i has thickness $b_i = (-1)^i y_i$, complex permittivity ϵ'_i , and complex permeability μ'_i ($i=1,2$). For the TM_0 solution, using a vector potential construction with $\vec{A} = \hat{z}\psi_i$, the electric and magnetic fields are

$$\nabla^2 \psi_i + k_i^2 \psi_i = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\vec{E}_i = -j\omega\mu'_i \vec{A}_i + \frac{1}{j\mu\epsilon'_i} \nabla(\nabla \cdot \vec{A}_i) = \frac{1}{j\omega\epsilon'_i} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \psi_i}{\partial x \partial z} \hat{x} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_i}{\partial y \partial z} \hat{y} + \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} + k_i^2 \right) \psi_i \hat{z} \right]$$

$$\vec{H}_i = \nabla \times \vec{A}_i = \frac{\partial \psi_i}{\partial y} \hat{x} - \frac{\partial \psi_i}{\partial x} \hat{y} \quad (3)$$

where μ'_i , ϵ'_i , and k_i^2 are the complex permeability, permittivity, and $\mu'_i \epsilon'_i \omega^2$ in the i th medium ($i=1$ is dielectric, $i=2$ is semiconductor). Requiring that $\partial/\partial x = 0$, and applying the boundary conditions $E_{zi} = 0$ at $y = y_1, y_2$ (conductor surfaces) and $\epsilon'_i E_{y1} = \epsilon'_2 E_{y2}$ and $E_{z1} = E_{z2}$ at $y=0$ (dielectric-semiconductor interface),

$$\psi_i = \psi_{0i} \sinh[\gamma_i(y-y_i)] e^{-\gamma z}; E_{yi} = -\frac{\gamma}{\gamma_i} E_{z0} \frac{\cosh[\gamma_i(y-y_i)]}{\sinh(\gamma_i y_i)} e^{-\gamma z} \quad (4,5)$$

$$E_{zi} = -E_{z0} \frac{\sinh[\gamma_i(y-y_i)]}{\sinh(\gamma_i y_i)} e^{-\gamma z}; H_{xi} = \frac{j\omega\epsilon'_i}{\gamma_i} E_{z0} \frac{\cosh[\gamma_i(y-y_i)]}{\sinh(\gamma_i y_i)} e^{-\gamma z} \quad (6,7)$$

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$$\gamma_i^2 + \gamma^2 + k_i^2 = 0 ; \sum_i \frac{\gamma_i}{\epsilon_i'} \tanh(\gamma_i b_i) = 0 \quad (8,9)$$

Combining (8) and (9) yields the dispersion relationship for the complex propagation constant. The dispersion equation can be written in terms of normalized variables by defining $\bar{\gamma} = \gamma/\beta_0 = \alpha + j\beta$, $\epsilon_i = \epsilon_i'/\epsilon_0$, and $\bar{\sigma} = \sigma/\omega\epsilon_0$ where $\beta_0 = \omega/c_0$, $\epsilon_i = \text{Re}(\epsilon_i')$, $\text{Im}(\epsilon_i') = -\sigma$, $c_0 = 1/\sqrt{\epsilon_0\mu_0}$, and ϵ_0, μ_0 are the free space permittivity and permeability. For a lossless dielectric medium, $\text{Im}(\epsilon_i') = 0$, semiconductor medium with conductivity σ , and non-magnetic medium, $\mu_i' = \mu_0$, the dispersion equation can be expressed as

$$f(\bar{\gamma}) = \frac{1}{\epsilon_{r1}} \sqrt{-\epsilon_{r1} - \bar{\gamma}^2} \tanh[\beta_0 b_1 \sqrt{-\epsilon_{r1} - \bar{\gamma}^2}] + \frac{1}{\epsilon_{r2} - j\bar{\sigma}} \sqrt{-\epsilon_{r2} + j\bar{\sigma} - \bar{\gamma}^2} \tanh[\beta_0 b_2 \sqrt{-\epsilon_{r2} + j\bar{\sigma} - \bar{\gamma}^2}] = 0 \quad (10)$$

by noting that $\tanh$ is an odd function of its argument.

For the TE_z solution a vector potential construction with $\vec{F} = \hat{z}\psi_i$ yields

$$\vec{E}_i = -\nabla_x \vec{F} = -\frac{\partial \psi_i}{\partial y} \hat{x} + \frac{\partial \psi_i}{\partial x} \hat{y} \quad (11)$$

$$\vec{H}_i = -j\omega\epsilon_i' + \frac{1}{j\omega\mu_i'} \nabla(\nabla \cdot \vec{F}_i) = \frac{1}{j\omega\mu_i'} \left[\frac{\partial^2 \psi_i}{\partial x \partial z} \hat{x} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi_i}{\partial y \partial z} \hat{y} + \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial z^2} + k_i^2 \right) \psi_i \right] \quad (12)$$

When the boundary conditions $E_{xi} = 0$ at $y=y_1, y_2$ and $H_{zi} = H_{z2}$ and $\mu_1' H_{y1} = \mu_2' H_{y2}$ at $y=0$ are imposed, (4)-(9) become altered as follows: $\sinh \rightarrow \cosh$ in (4); for (5)-(7) interchange E and H on LHS, $E_{z0} \rightarrow E_{z0}$, $\cosh \rightarrow \sinh$, multiply respectively by $\gamma_i/j\omega\mu_i'$, $\gamma_i/j\omega\mu_i'$, $-\gamma_i/j\omega\epsilon_i'$; in (9) $\bar{\gamma} \rightarrow \bar{\gamma}$ and $\epsilon_i' \rightarrow \mu_i'$. The

dispersion relation for $\bar{\gamma}$ is given by (10) is the coefficients of the $\tanh$ functions are interchanged and their denominators removed.

Numerical Results: Muller's method is used to determine the $\bar{\gamma} = \bar{\gamma}_n$ eigenvalue solutions to $f(\bar{\gamma})=0$ in (10) where $n=0, 1, 2, \dots$ indicates the particular branch ordered according to decreasing β , $n=0$ being the lowest or fundamental branch with the largest slowing factor $\bar{\beta}$. The notation for n agrees with [1] for TM_z in the $\sigma = 0$ limit where $n=0$ is the quasi-TEM case. Solutions to (10) are sought which have $\bar{\beta} = \text{Im}(\bar{\gamma}) > 0$ to assure propagation in the $+z$ -direction. Figures 2-5 give the $\bar{\gamma}$ results as $\bar{\beta}$ and α versus f plotted in each figure. $\bar{\beta} > 1$ indicates phase velocity relative to that for free space. In order to find if the two-layer loaded waveguide provides improvement over its constituent material dielectric constants, $\bar{\beta}/\max\{\epsilon_{r1}, \epsilon_{r2}\}$ should be evaluated. For illustrative purposes and to allow comparison to the fundamental mode results in [1] (agreement with their Fig. 3 results is within 5%), the $\sigma > 0$ calculations are done here for $\epsilon_{r1} = 4.5$, $\epsilon_{r2} = 12$, $b_1 = 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, $b_2 = 190 \mu\text{m}$, and $\sigma = 10^{-3} \text{U/m}$. The nominal values of ϵ_{ri} chosen could represent SiO_2 -Si layers.

Consider $\bar{\alpha}$ and α first in Figs. 2 and 3. As n increases or f decreases, $\bar{\alpha}$ and $d\bar{\alpha}/df$ increase (not shown). For TM_z the $n=0$ case has $d\bar{\alpha}/df$ much smaller than the other branches. Compared to $d\bar{\alpha}/df$ below 30 GHz, $d\alpha/df$ is

relatively small at 140 GHz. This $\bar{\alpha}$ behavior causes the un-normalized attenuation constant $\alpha = \beta_0 \bar{\alpha}$ in Figs. 2 and 3 to increase gently with f . $d\alpha/df$ roughly decreases with increasing f , a trend especially noticeable for TM_z. Except for the $n=0$ TE_z branch, $d\alpha/df$ is very small for the $n \geq 1$ branches. Slowing factor $\bar{\beta}$ decreases as n increases, the reverse trend as seen for α (or $\bar{\alpha}$). The change in slowing $\Delta\bar{\beta}/\bar{\beta}$ over the 10 to 140 GHz range decreases as n increases for TM_z. Such behavior is only observable for the $n=0$ TE_z branch which has a 34.3% change, the other branches exhibiting little $\bar{\beta}$ change over f in comparison. Comparison of the TM_z and TE_z results (same n) show that $\bar{\beta}$ is significantly larger for TM_z and that $\bar{\alpha}$ is larger for TE_z, these differences being especially apparent at lower f . Figures 4 and 5 graph the γ results for $\sigma < 0$, with values of $\epsilon_{r1} = \epsilon_{r2} = 12$, $b_1 = 0.3 \mu\text{m}$, $b_2 = 200 \mu\text{m}$, and $\sigma = -10^{-3} / \text{m}$ having been chosen. Nominal values of $\bar{\epsilon}_{ri}$ could correspond to depleted GaAs-GaAs layers. The behavior of the TM_z and TE_z results for an active medium semiconductor are similar to the resistive medium behavior (Figs. 2 and 3) in that $\bar{\beta}$ and α for $\sigma > 0$ and $\bar{\beta}$ and $-\alpha$ for $\sigma < 0$ have similar dependences on n and f . One important difference is that $\bar{\beta}$ does not necessarily increase with increasing n at lower f ($f \sim 40$ GHz). The second major difference is that for an excitation involving several TM_z and TE_z modes, when $\sigma > 0$ the lowest n branch will be favored due to attenuation, whereas for $\sigma < 0$ the higher n branches will become dominant as their gain causes a larger difference in wave growth over the lower n branches.

Discussion: We have shown that $\bar{\beta}$ may be very sizable at millimeter wave frequencies, corresponding to effective relative dielectric constants exceeding several hundred. For the applications mentioned in the introduction of this paper, the attenuation found may be too large for some of them. New approaches may be necessary such as combining the slowing effect with an active medium to allow wave growth during propagation which can compensate the attenuation. The slowing found here when combined with that obtainable using proper geometric arrangements such as a meander microstrip line would allow overall slowing factors exceeding 1000. New applications involving electron beam-rf interactions in solids, especially semiconductors, would be possible. One potential application is in a solid state semiconductor magnetron which could have very high electron densities (orders of magnitude above the intrinsic level) and might be able to overcome the possible α limitations discussed.

References

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Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5